

COMPLEX FORMATION BY ASCORBIC ACID WITH FORMALDEHYDE.

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Formaldehyde is found to form a complex with ascorbic acid as shown by two independent methods of estimation of ascorbic acid, the titration with dichlorophenol-indophenol and the titration with iodine solution. The complex formation has been found to vary with the p_H of the solution containing the ascorbic acid. Quantitative estimations of formaldehyde also support the above conclusion.

During the study of the influence of various substances on ascorbic acid oxidation it was observed that formaldehyde lessens, to a striking extent, the capacity of ascorbic acid for consuming the 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol dye, even in the initial stages, irrespective of the presence or other wise of added Cu^{+} . This was found to be interesting, as many substances that occur in plant and animal tissues were on the other hand found to possess inhibitory influence on ascorbic acid oxidation to varying degrees, as reported by Krishnamurthy and Giri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 191). Further, it was found strange that such a powerful reducing agent as formaldehyde behaves like this towards ascorbic acid. Hence in this paper are given the results of the study in detail of the effect of formaldehyde on ascorbic acid, in order to settle the mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For determining the percentage of vitamin that has disappeared on treatment with formaldehyde, 10 ml. of the buffer of the appropriate p_H were kept in a conical flask, the required volume of formaldehyde solution was added along with enough water to make the total volume 20 ml. The mixture was shaken well and kept in an electrically controlled thermostat at 37° . Then 5 ml. of the solution containing 5 mg. of ascorbic acid were added, and after shaking well, 2 ml. of the mixture were pipetted out into 1 ml. of glacial acetic acid and titrated immediately with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol solution from a microburette. For the iodine estimation, 2 ml. of the mixture, added to 1 ml. glacial acetic acid, were titrated with $N/500$ -solution of iodine from a microburette using starch as the indicator. Pure and redistilled formaldehyde was used in this investigation.

Estimation of formaldehyde in the reaction mixture was done according to the following method (Sutton, "Volumetric Analysis," 11th Ed., p. 373). 2 ml. of the reaction mixture were pipetted out into

a conical flask containing 10 ml. of $N/10$ solution of iodine and immediately treated with a solution of sodium hydroxide drop by drop until the liquid became clear yellow. After 10 minutes enough dilute hydrochloric acid was added to liberate the uncombined iodine, which was then titrated back with $N/10$ -sodium thiosulphate solution.

Effect of varying the Concentrations of Formaldehyde on Ascorbic Acid.—The percentage of ascorbic acid disappearing at p_H 5.6 on the addition of formaldehyde initially, as well as after 30 and 60 minutes, was determined both by titration with the indophenol dye and $N/500$ -iodine solution, and the results obtained by both the methods are presented in the following table. Blank experiments were performed and it was found that formaldehyde alone in the reaction mixture under the experimental conditions, does not consume the dye. However, it was found that it takes up 0.15 ml. of iodine solution irrespective of the concentration of the formaldehyde used, and evidently this is required for the production of the blue colour with starch, which was used as the indicator in these titrations.

TABLE I.

 $p_H = 5.6$

% Conc. of H·CHO in the mixture per 100 ml.	Percentage of ascorbic acid disappearing.					
	Estimation with I_2 .			Estimation with dye.		
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.
0	—	34%	50%	—	32%	52%
0.072 g.	4%	34	48	6%	36	50
0.144	8	34	48	10	38	54
0.288	12	36	50	16	38	52
0.364	14	38	50	18	40	54
0.72	30	50	60	32	52	62
1.08	38	56	64	46	58	66
1.44	46	60	66	54	64	70
1.84	52	64	72	64	70	76
3.68	72	80	82	82	86	88
5.52	82	84	88	90	92	92
7.36	82	84	84	88	88	90
9.20	84	88	88	90	92	92

The reaction mixture consisted of 10 ml. of $M/5$ -acetate buffer of p_H 5.6, 5 mg. of ascorbic acid, formaldehyde solution, and water to make up the total volume to 25 ml.

The results in the above table show clearly that there is a decrease in concentration of the ascorbic acid immediately after the addition of formaldehyde. Though this decrease increases with the increase in the concentration of formaldehyde, the ascorbic acid does not, however, completely disappear on the addition of a high concentration of formaldehyde. Further, the disappearance of ascorbic acid is not due to oxidation, as it is

observed only initially, and later with time, it is only gradual. It is clear, therefore, that the disappearance of ascorbic acid initially is not due to oxidation, but must be due to complex formation. These results also show clearly that the percentage of ascorbic acid disappearing after 30 and 60 minutes is not so much as is observed initially, and hence must be due to the spontaneous oxidation of the vitamin. It is also evident that after the initial complex formation, the rate of oxidation of the residual vitamin is almost the same as would be observed with ascorbic acid by itself.

Effect of Formaldehyde on Ascorbic Acid at Different p_H .—The effect of formaldehyde on ascorbic acid at different p_H was studied, and the results thereof are represented graphically. For this also the amount of ascorbic acid disappearing was determined both by titration with the indophenol dye and *N*/500-iodine solution, from acetate and phosphate buffers of the appropriate p_H . At each p_H it was established that the concentration of formaldehyde does not alter in any way by performing blank estimations under the experimental conditions.

The figure shows that the percentage of disappearance of ascorbic acid

is not the same at all p_H and that it attains a maximal value at about p_H 5.3, it declines rapidly up to about p_H 7 and again after p_H 8 it shows a gradual rise, though to a limited extent. It is also clear that the maximum disappearance is at p_H 5.3 and the minimum is at about 6.5. Further it is found that the complex formation is more in the acid range than at the neutral p_H , and that at the alkaline p_H also, there is complex formation though not to such an extent as at the acid p_H .

It has also been established quantitatively that formaldehyde also undergoes decrease in concentration as a result of the complex formation with ascorbic acid. For this purpose 20 mg. of ascorbic acid were taken in a buffer of p_H 5.6 and treated with formaldehyde, keeping alongside blanks with formaldehyde and ascorbic acid of the same concentrations. The formaldehyde was estimated by the method described, and the amount of iodine used up by ascorbic acid was also simultaneously determined. The

results in Table II show that formaldehyde decreases on treatment with ascorbic acid.

TABLE II.

Ascorbic acid in the blank	...	...	20.0 mg.
Formaldehyde in the blank	...	...	47.5
Ascorbic acid in the reaction mixture	...	...	9.75
Formaldehyde in the reaction mixture	...	...	45.3

Similar experiments were performed a number of times and in every case a decrease in formaldehyde concentration was noticed. It is significant, however, that ascorbic acid is never used up completely in the complex formation even though a large amount of formaldehyde is used.

DISCUSSION.

The results presented in this paper show that formaldehyde immediately on addition reduces the concentration of ascorbic acid, as is shown by the reduction in its dye and iodine consuming capacities, and that this is due to complex formation with ascorbic acid.

This observation is of particular interest, since both formaldehyde and ascorbic acid are synthesised and are present in the plant tissues, and perhaps as a result of this complex formation, further syntheses might be brought about. Further, it is noteworthy that this complex formation is dependent on the p_n of the medium, the acid range favouring it considerably, whereas in the neutral range it is minimum, tending to increase in the alkaline range.

Kurin (*Biokhimiya*, 1937, 2, 127) while studying the catalytic effect of vitamin-C in the synthesis of carbon chains observed that the addition of formaldehyde to *iso*-ascorbic acid greatly diminishes the reducing power of the latter, and concluded that apparently an addition product is formed, but adduced no evidence to support his observation. West and Ney (*Science*, 1936, 84, 294) found that ascorbic acid catalyses the conversion of formaldehyde to reducing sugars in presence of calcium hydroxide.

The results show conclusively that ascorbic acid forms a complex with formaldehyde. Acetaldehyde and paraformaldehyde have been found to be without a similar effect.

Further work on the isolation and study of the complex is in progress.

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